

Synthesis, Characterisation and Coordinating Properties of a New Benzimidazolylpyrazole : Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) Complexes of 5-Methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole

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The synthesis, characterisation (mass, ir and pmr) and coordinating properties of a new imidazolylpyrazole, viz. 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole (MBP) containing the well-known chelating grouping $-N=C-C=N-$ are reported. A host of electrolytic metallic complexes, $M(MBP)_nX_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($M = Co/Ni/Cu$; $n = 2$ or 3 ; $X =$ a counterion like Cl^- , Br^- , NO_3^- , I^- , ClO_4^- etc.) of the title ligand identified by physicochemical techniques are described. Magnetic and electronic spectral features classify all the species as magnetically normal high-spin six-coordinate complexes with an overall octahedral geometry. Epr spectral data of some of the Cu^{II} species have identified the examined complexes as tetragonally distorted octahedral species associated with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state, the degree of exchange coupling being dependent on the counterion (X). Ir spectral data recommend that MBP exhibits a neutral bidentate function through the pyrazolyl and the imidazolyl tertiary nitrogens in forming complexes with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} salts. Ir data also reveal that for the tris-chelated species of Co^{II} and Ni^{II} with MN_6 environment and for some of the aqua-bis-chelated species with MN_4O_2 chromophore, the counterion (X) retains its ionic character and for majority of the bis-species, $[M(MBP)_2X_2]$, the anion (X) is coordinated at least in the solid state.

Pyrazole (1,2-diazole) is isomeric with imidazole (1,3-diazole), an integral part of the well-known histidine molecule, which provides an important binding site in biological systems, playing a vital role in metal-protein interactions^{1,2}. During recent years, a substantial amount of research has been generated around the studies involving the coordination characteristics of both imidazole- and pyrazole-derived (model) ligands from various aspects in order to have meaningful information regarding the binding sites of the in vivo metal ions. The vigorous development in the coordination chemistry of pyrazole-based ligands has merited two review articles^{3,4}, the more recent one⁴ refers significant work of Saha *et al.* The report of the coordination pattern of ligands containing two different *N*-heterocycles by complexation with transition metal ions has enriched the literature^{5,6} which also includes work from our laboratory⁷. In continuation of our recent research⁸ on pyrazole-containing ligands with special reference to the ligational behaviour of pyridyl-pyrazole^{7a} and pyrimidyl pyrazole^{7b,7c,7b}, the present communication reports the synthesis, characterisation and coordinating properties of a new imidazolylpyrazole, viz. 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole

(Fig. 1, hereinafter abbreviated as MBP) by complexation with transition metal ions. The identification of a host of tris- and bis-complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} salts by various spectroscopic methods forms the major part of the publication.

Fig 1 5-Methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole (MBP)

Results and Discussion

The electron ionisation mass spectrum of the title ligand, shows a molecular ion peak (M^+) at m/z 198 with 100% intensity (Fig. 2). This datum is happily compatible with the expected molecular weight of the compound, i.e. 198 which, in turn, agrees exactly with the molecular formula of the ligand, MBP, as $C_{11}N_4H_{10}$, identical with its empirical composition as evidenced from C, H and N analyses. The other most prominent peak appears at m/z 169 with nearly 80% intensity; the less

significant low intensity peaks are found at m/z 170 and 142. Based on the peak positions and their relative intensities, a fragmentation pattern can be formulated for the formation of different less-stable components of the reported benzimidazolyl pyrazole. The envisaged fragmentation patterns or pathways are schematically shown in Fig. 3 with probable mechanisms which are self-explanatory. The mass spectral features along with the recommended fragmentation pathways support⁹ the proposed structural formulation of the synthesised ligand as 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole (Fig. 1).

The pmr spectral data recorded in (DMSO- d_6) are in comfortable agreement with the proposed structural formulation of 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole (Fig. 1, shown with δ values). A sharp three-proton singlet (Fig. 4) at δ 2.269 corresponds to three methyl protons at C-5 of pyrazole ring. The lone pyrazole proton at C-4 appears as a singlet at δ 6.568. The spectral signals at δ 2.464 and 3.344 are conceivably due to DMSO and HDO respectively. The aromatic protons (i.e. at 4', 5', 6' and 7' positions) of the benzimidazolyl moiety appear at δ 7.122, 7.416 and 7.547. A sharp two-proton singlet at δ 7.122 is due to aa' protons at C-4' and C-7', a doublet appearing at δ 7.416 and 7.547 are due to bb' aromatic protons of C-5' and C-6' positions of benzimidazole ring. The N-H protons of the pyrazole and the benzimidazole moieties do not appear in the pmr spectrum; this can be ascribed to its high lability and rapid deuterio-exchange phenomenon in DMSO- d_6 . Thus the pmr data unambiguously recommend the proposed structural formula of the title ligand, MBP (Fig. 1).

The reported bis- and tris-complexes of cobalt(II) conform to the general empirical

composition, $\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, NO_3^- , ClO_4^- , I^-), $\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_3\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$) as revealed from elemental analyses (Table 1). The molar conductance values (λ_m) of 115–203 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ for the methanolic solutions of all the Co^{II} complexes indicate their 1 : 2 electrolytic nature¹⁰ at least in solution of the said solvent. The values for bis-species can be reconciled only in terms of complete solvolysis as

where, $\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, I^- , NO_3^- , ClO_3^- . A lower Λ_m (115 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) for the tris-cobalt(II) sulphate may be due to lesser ionic mobility of the anionic moiety.

The μ_B values (Table 1) of the reported bis- and tris-cobalt(II) complexes lie in the range 4.29–4.91 B.M.; the somewhat lower values (4.29–4.42 B.M.) for some of the species are ascribed to the presence of an orbital singlet ground state with a distorted octahedral environment¹¹. The μ_B values can only suggest that the reported complexes belong to a group of lower symmetry (C_2). The diffuse reflectance spectra of the bis- and tris-cobalt(II) complexes are characterised by two main bands (except for $\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2\text{I}_2$) appearing at 8 575–9 165 and 20 000–21 275 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (ν_3) transitions¹² respectively, in a pseudo-octahedral environment. In case of $\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2\text{I}_2$, the ν_3 band (in terms of regular O_h symmetry) appears as a strong shoulder near 20 000 cm^{-1} , which might be due to mixing with a CT band appearing near 27 780 cm^{-1} . All the tris-complexes show this CT absorption near 27 000–29 000 cm^{-1} along with the bis-perchlorate where the band appears as a shoulder. The bis-

Fig. 2. Mass spectrum (70 eV) of 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole.

complexes show low intensity bands near $37\,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be assigned as CT absorption associated with ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions. The values of LF parameters, Dq ($973\text{--}1\,039\text{ cm}^{-1}$), B ($827\text{--}889\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and β ($0.85\text{--}0.91$) for the reported complexes, calculated by known relationships^{13,14} are consistent¹⁵ with those observed for spin-free octahedral Co^{II} species reported earlier. The d.r.s. of $[\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ shows an intense shoulder near $16\,900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is not due to ν_2 transition, but is likely to arise from spin-forbidden transition¹⁶, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(G)$. The pink to orange solutions of the reported bis- and tris-complexes in DMSO exhibit spectral bands at $9\,090\text{--}10\,235$ (ν_1) ($\epsilon = 40.1\text{--}87.9$) and $20\,410\text{--}21\,710$ (ν_3) ($\epsilon = 25.0\text{--}47.7$); the bis-iodo complex, however, shows no band in the ν_3 region possibly due to strong CT absorption in the same region.

Fig. 3. Fragmentation pathways with probable mechanisms from the mass spectrum of MBP.

The effective magnetic moment values (2.56–2.77 B.M.) at 30° for $[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_3]\text{X}_2$ and $[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_2\text{X}_2]$ are grossly commensurate with six-coordinate spin-free Ni^{II} complexes¹⁷. The molar conductance values in methanolic solutions lie in the range $154\text{--}159$ (bis-complexes) and $194\text{--}218\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$ (tris-species classifying the reported species as 1 : 2 electrolytes¹⁰ in the said solvent. The diffuse reflectance spectra of all the reported Ni^{II} species consist of three main bands appearing at $10\,205\text{--}10\,415$, $17\,095\text{--}18\,180$ and $26\,660\text{--}28\,570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable¹⁸ to transitions ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 respectively, in a regular O_h symmetry. The ν_3 band due to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ transition appearing in the range $26\,660\text{--}28\,570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ trail to the higher energy uv region; this is possibly due to its mixing up with CT absorption. The calculated¹⁹ band (ν_3) positions are very near to the observed ones, and hence, the assignment might be taken as reasonably correct. The weak spectral bands appearing as shoulders around $13\,700\text{--}13\,890\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the tris-chelates of Ni^{II} may be attributed to spin-forbidden transitions²⁰. For the bis-chelates, a high intensity band appears in the uv region ($31\,250\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which may be assigned as CT absorption associated with ligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. The LF parameters calculated from the diagonal sum rule¹⁹ (assuming O_h symmetry) furnish values of Dq ($1\,020\text{--}1\,042\text{ cm}$), B ($900\text{--}991\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and β ($0.83\text{--}0.92$) adding tacit support for the proposed octahedral geometry²¹ for the reported Ni^{II} species. The values of ν_1/ν_2 lying in the range $1.66\text{--}1.78$ offer further evidence for an octahedral environment²³. Electronic spectral data of the methanolic solutions of the Ni^{II} complexes consist of two main bands located at $10\,205\text{--}10\,870$ and $16\,130\text{--}18\,180\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which may conceivably be assigned to ν_1 and ν_2 transitions in an average O_h symmetry. The calculated molar extinction coefficients of the order of $11.2\text{--}22.7\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$ give additional support to the octahedral arrangements²² of the ligands in the metal chelates. The absence of the ν_3 band in the spectral data in solution may be due to an intense internal $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions of the ligand or due to CT absorption, arising from $M \rightarrow L$ via the π -antibonding level of the heterocyclic ligand(s)²³. The strong band at $33\,785\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with high molar extinction values ($\epsilon = 157.6\text{--}194.0\text{ cm}^{-1}\text{ mol}^{-1}$) in the spectra of the bis-chelates of Ni^{II} in methanol may originate from charge transfer.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Yield %	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)					μ_{eff} B.M.	Λ_M^{**} $\Omega^{-1}\text{cm}^2\text{mol}^{-1}$
			Metal	C	H	N	X		
[Co(MBP) ₂ Cl ₂]	Pink	75	11.2 (11.4)	50.2 (49.7)	3.8 (3.7)	21.3 (21.5)	13.5 (13.2)	4.29	151
[Co(MBP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Pink	65	10.2 (10.4)	45.6 (45.5)	3.4 (3.2)	24.2 ^a (24.4)	—	4.35	203
[Co(MBP) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂]	Pink violet	55	9.0 (8.8)	40.4 (40.2)	3.0 (2.9)	17.1 (17.0)	10.9 ^b (10.5)	4.34	167
[Co(MBP) ₂ h ₂]	Yellow	60	8.3 (8.3)	37.2 (37.4)	2.8 (2.5)	15.8 (15.5)	35.8 (35.6)	4.81	198
[Co(MBP) ₃ Br ₂]	Pale pink	55	7.2 (7.7)	48.7 (48.2)	3.7 (3.4)	20.6 (20.3)	19.7 (19.3)	4.41	174
[Co(MBP) ₃]SO ₄	Light pink	60	7.9 (8.4)	52.9 (51.9)	4.0 (3.9)	22.4 (21.9)	4.3 ^b (3.9)	4.42	115
[Co(MBP) ₃]Cl ₂	Pink	55	8.1 (7.9)	54.7 (54.4)	4.1 (3.8)	23.2 (23.6)	9.8 (9.5)	4.41	187
[Ni(MBP) ₃]Cl ₂	Bluish violet	55	8.1 (7.7)	54.7 (54.5)	4.1 (3.9)	23.2 (23.5)	9.8 (9.6)	2.61	134
[Ni(MBP) ₃](NO ₃) ₂	Bluish violet	65	7.6 (8.0)	51.0 (50.7)	3.9 (3.6)	25.2 ^a (25.1)	—	2.77	194
[Ni(MBP) ₃]h ₂	Grey yellowish	65	6.5 (6.9)	43.7 (43.3)	3.3 (3.6)	18.5 (18.3)	28.0 (27.6)	2.67	189
[Ni(MBP) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂	Bluish violet	65	6.9 (7.0)	46.5 (46.7)	3.5 (3.7)	19.7 (19.9)	8.4 ^b (8.2)	2.72	218
[Ni(MBP) ₃](BF ₄) ₂	Blue	75	7.1 (7.3)	47.9 (47.4)	3.6 (3.3)	20.3 (20.1)	—	2.60	208
[Ni(MBP) ₂ (SCN) ₂]	Blue	60	10.3 (9.8)	46.3 (45.8)	3.5 (3.3)	24.5 ^c (24.4)	11.2 (11.0)	2.56	154
[Ni(MBP) ₂ Br ₂]	Light blue	60	9.5 (9.1)	42.9 (42.7)	3.2 (3.0)	18.2 (18.1)	26.0 (26.2)	2.67	159
[Cu(MBP) ₂ Cl ₂]	Light green	50	12.0 (11.7)	49.8 (49.6)	3.8 (3.6)	21.1 (20.8)	13.4 (13.1)	1.72	193
[Cu(MBP) ₂ Br ₂]	Dark green	60	10.2 (9.9)	42.6 (42.4)	3.2 (3.4)	18.1 (18.2)	25.8 (25.6)	1.92	71
[Cu(MBP) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂]	Deep green	60	10.9 (10.3)	45.2 (45.4)	3.4 (3.2)	24.0 ^a (23.6)	—	1.88	133
[Cu(MBP) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₂]- (ClO ₄) ₂	Yellowish green	75	9.1 (8.6)	38.0 (37.7)	3.4 (3.3)	16.1 ^b (16.3)	10.2 (10.1)	1.84	137
[Cu(MBP) ₂ (BF ₄) ₂]	Bright green	50	10.0 (9.8)	41.7 (41.1)	3.2 (3.3)	17.7 (17.5)	—	1.80	79
[Cu(MBP) ₂ SO ₄]. 2H ₂ O	Green	60	10.7 (10.5)	44.6 (44.8)	4.1 (3.9)	18.9 (18.7)	5.4 ^b (5.6)	2.12	113

*At 303 K. **In 1.0×10^{-3} M methanolic solution for Co^{II} and Ni^{II} or DMF solution for Cu^{II} complexes.^aIncluding N present in nitrate; ^bS %; ^cincluding N present in thiocyanate.

The bis-complexes, $\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-, \text{Br}^-, \text{ClO}_4^-, \text{NO}_3^-, \text{BF}_4^-$ and $1/2 \text{SO}_4^{2-}$; $n = 0.2$) show λ_m values in the range $71\text{--}193 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ in DMF (Table 1) classifying the complexes either as 1 : 1 or 1 : 2 electrolytes¹⁰ depending upon the extent of solvolysis due to either partial or total release of anions (X) in the said solvent. The μ_B values of 1.72–2.12 B.M. at 30° for the reported Cu^{II} complexes are in accord with their distorted octahedral configurations²⁴ as expected. The diffuse reflectance spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ are characterised by a broad asymmetric band appearing around $14\,925\text{--}15\,875 \text{cm}^{-1}$ suggesting that all the three expected transitions, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}(v_1)$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}(v_2)$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g(v_3)$ in D_{4h} symmetry lie within one broad envelope and that distortion is not appreciable from octahedral symmetry. A recognisable band around $27\,025\text{--}27\,395 \text{cm}^{-1}$, probably originating from charge transfer has been observed in the d.r.s. of all the reported Cu^{II} complexes. All the bis- Cu^{II} complexes of MBP are reasonably regarded as tetragonally distorted octahedral species^{25,26}. The DMSO solutions of the Cu^{II} species exhibit $d\text{-}d$ spectral bands around $12\,985\text{--}15\,105 \text{cm}^{-1}$ indicating that there is no significant change in the stereochemistry of the complexes on dissolution even in a donor solvent.

TABLE 2—EPR SPECTRAL DATA OF SOME Cu^{II} COMPLEXES

Compd.	g_1	g_2	g_{av}	G
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	2.062	2.151	2.091	2.43
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	2.042	2.191	2.092	4.54
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	2.032	2.121	2.062	3.78
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{OH})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	2.032	2.218	2.064	4.00

The epr data (Table 2) on some of the reported Cu^{II} complexes have been interpreted according to Kneubuhl's method²⁷. The data along with representative spectral curves (Figs. 5 and 6) are useful for estimating the presence or absence of significant exchange coupling²⁷. As the G values for the bromo- and the perchlorate-complexes are ≥ 4 , their exchange coupling is less than those in other two cases. The exchange coupling might be considered as feeble in $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$ having a G value of 3.78, but for the chloro-complex, high exchange coupling is present ($G = 2.43$). It is clear, therefore, that the degree of exchange coupling is dependent on the counterion (X) in the examined Cu^{II} species. The data also clearly reveal that in all

the cases $g_{11} > g_1$ which is characteristic of tetragonal symmetry with $d_{x^2-y^2}$ ground state²⁸. Again the value of $2.092 \geq g_{av} \geq 2.062$ points out unambiguously for a tetragonally distorted octahedral symmetry with a $d_{x^2-y^2}$ state rather than d_{z^2} ²⁷.

Fig. 4. ${}^1\text{H}$ nmr spectrum of MBP in $\text{DMSO-}d_6$

The structural formulation of the ligand MB (Fig. 1) and construction of molecular model of the same suggest that the tertiary nitrogen atoms of the pyrazolyl- and the imidazolyl-ring systems are the only available bonding sites for complexation with a metal ion forming a stable five-membered ring. This expectation is indirectly shown to be true from significant changes in the ir band frequencies in the metal complexes compared to those of the free ligand. A strong band appearing at $1\,570 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (in the uncomplexed ligand spectrum) assigned to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ of the diazole systems is shifted towards higher frequency region ($\Delta\nu = 5\text{--}15 \text{cm}^{-1}$) in its metal complexes, indicating thereby the expected participation of both pyrazolyl and imidazolyl ring nitrogens^{28,29}. Similar positive shifts of $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ vibrations have previously been reported³⁰ for transition metal complexes of N -heterocyclic bases; $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}}$ of the pyrazole ring also suffers positive shift ($\Delta\nu = 5\text{--}30 \text{cm}^{-1}$) indicating tacit support to the participation of the tertiary pyrazolyl nitrogen. In the far-ir spectra, the appearance of bands appearing around 300cm^{-1} ($290\text{--}320 \text{cm}^{-1}$) can safely be assigned to $\nu_{\text{M}=\text{N}}(\text{diazole})$ ³¹. The ir spectral data also furnish meaningful clues with regard to the mode of

attachment of counterion (X) in the reported metallic complexes. Some of the characteristic and relevant anion frequencies with probable assignments and approximate symmetry³² are sorted out in Table 3. It is revealed that in all the trispecies, the counterion (X) obviously retains its ionic character while in the bis-complexes of MBP, the anionic component (Cl^- , Br^- , NCS^- , BF_4^- , ClO_4^- and SO_4^{2-}) is coordinated except in $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ where it (X) retains ionic character. It is reasonably inferred, therefore, that for the tris-chelates of the primary ligand (MBP), is exhibited a neutral bidentate function all the six positions of the octahedron being occupied by the donor nitrogens of the three molecules of the title ligand (MBP), while for the bis-species, two primary ligand molecules (MBP) occupy four positions of the octahe-

dron and the *trans*-axial sites are taken up either by the coordinated anions or water molecules, although such propositions are highly conjectural in absence of X-ray crystallographic data.

Fig 5. Epr spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

TABLE 3—SOME CHARACTERISTIC ANION FREQUENCIES WITH PROBABLE ASSIGNMENT(S) AND APPROXIMATE SYMMETRY FOR THE COMPLEXES

Complex	Anion bands (cm^{-1})	Assignments	Symmetry
$[\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_3]\text{SO}_4$	1 150–1 060bs	ν_3 of an ionic sulphate	T_d
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_3](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	1 100–1 095bs 630bs	ν_3 of an ionic perchlorate ν_4	T_d
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$	1 405–1 380bm 815bs	ν_3 of an ionic nitrate ν_4	D_{3h}
$[\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	280m	$\nu_{\text{Co-Cl}}$	—
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Br}_2]$	285s	$\nu_{\text{Ni-Br}}$	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	280s	$\nu_{\text{Cu-Cl}}$	—
$[\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$	1 185m 1 115w 1 090s 1 035m 625bs	ν_1 Splitting ν_3 of σ -bonded perchlorate ν_4	C_{3v}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	1 130–1 070bs 630vs	ν_3 of anionic perchlorate	T_d
$[\text{Co}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2]$	1 400bm 1 310m 820m	Components of ν_3 of monodentate nitrate ν_2	C_{2v}
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$	1 160vs 1 100vs 1 050vs 1 010s	Splitting ν_3 of bonded sulphate ν_1	C_{2v}
$[\text{Ni}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{SCN})_2]$	2 100bs 810s 470 cm^{-1}	ν_1 ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ stretching) ν_3 ($\nu_{\text{C-S}}$ stretching) of N-bonded thiocyanate ν_{NCS}	
$[\text{Cu}(\text{MBP})_2(\text{BF}_4)_2]$	1 095m 1 050s 1 035m	Splitting components of ν_3 of a monodentate fluoroborate	C_{3v}

Experimental

Materials : All the chemicals used were B.D.H. quality. Metal(II) bromide, iodide, perchlorate, fluoborate and thiocyanate were either generated in situ or prepared from metal(II) carbonates and the appropriate acids/salts and were used after recrystallisation. Spectrograde solvents were used for spectral and conductance measurements.

5-Methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole : The title ligand, 5-methyl-3-(2'-benzimidazolyl)pyrazole (MBP) was prepared by solid state condensation around 130–60° of *o*-phenylenediamine (0.1 mol) and 5(3)-methylpyrazole-3(5)-carboxylic acid³³ (0.1 mol) following the general method of synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives with proper modifications. The shining white needle-shaped crystals of the pure product was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 309–10° (Found : C, 65.94; H, 4.95; N, 27.88. C₁₁N₄H₁₀ calcd. for : C, 66.60; H, 5.05; N, 28.28%).

Fig. 6. Epr spectrum of [Cu(MBP)₂(OH₂)₂](ClO₄)₂.

Preparation of the Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} salts with MBP : Both tris- and bis-complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with different counterions were prepared by interaction of the ligand, MBP and the hydrated metal(II) salt, MX₂.nH₂O, in appropriate mole ratio (0.003 : 0.001 for tris-species and 0.002 : 0.001 for bis-species) in hot ethanolic solution (except in the case of sulphate complexes, where water was used as solvent). In case of both bis- and tris-complexes of Co^{II} and Ni^{II}, refluxing was necessary for ~1 h and the concentrated refluxate on cooling to room temperature (25°) precipitated the desired complex as microcrystalline coloured product (Table 1), while Cu(MBP)₂X₂, in each case, was obtained within few minutes of mixing the ligand and the Cu^{II} salt in aqueous ethanolic solution. All the solid complexes were collected and dried as usual. C, H

and N were estimated in a Perkin-Elmer 240 elemental analyser or in a Thomas CH Analyser 35. The metal contents were determined by conventional gravimetric methods, viz. nickel as nickel(II) dimethyl glyoximate, cobalt as anhydrous cobalt(II) sulphate and copper as Cu(en)₂HgI₄. The anions (halogen, sulphate etc.) were estimated by standard procedures³⁴.

Mass spectrum was recorded on an AEIMS spectrometer (70 eV), pmr spectrum (DMSO-d₆) on a Brooker AM 300 L superconducting FT NMR spectrometer (300 MHz) and esr spectra (solid state) on a Varian EPR E 112 spectrometer. Various physicochemical measurements such as magnetic susceptibility, molar conductance, electronic (both d.r.s. and solution) and ir spectral studies were carried out as described earlier¹⁶.

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References

1. H. SIGEL, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 411.
2. R. J. SUNDBERG and R. B. MARTIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1974, **74**, 471.
3. S. TROFIMENKO, *Chem. Rev.*, 1972, **72**, 500.
4. S. TROFIMENKO, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **34**, 116, and references (nos. 686-710) therein containing the work of SAHA *et al.*
5. S. P. GHOSH and A. MISRA, *J. Indian Chem Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 791.
6. A. S. ABUSHAMLESH and H. A. GOODWIN, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1988, **41**, 873, and references therein.
7. (a) N. SAHA and S. K. KAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1989, **66**, 521; (b) N. SAHA and D. MUKHERJEE, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 47; (c) *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1987, **137**, 161; (d) *Transition. Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 156.
8. N. SAHA, A. SAHA, S. CHOUDHURY, T. C. W. MAK, T. BANERJEE and P. ROYCHOUDHURY, *Polyhedron*, 1992, **11**, 2341.

9. (a) I. L. FINAR, "Organic Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1980, Vol. 1, (b) ASFON, "Mass spectra and Isotopes", 1942.
10. W. J. GEARY, *Coord Chem Rev.*, 1971, 7, 81.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, 4, 1042.
12. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 318.
13. C. J. BALLHAUSEN, "Introduction to Ligand Field Theory", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1962, p. 256.
14. C. K. JORGENSEN, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, 5, 33.
15. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 324.
16. N. SAHA, A. K. ADAK and A. MISRA, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-org. Chem.*, 1988, 18, 989.
17. F. A. COTTON and G. WILKINSON, "Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", 5th. ed., Wiley, New York, 1988, p. 745.
18. A. D. LEIHR and C. J. BALLHAUSEN, *Ann. Phys.*, 1959, 6, 134.
19. (a) O. BOSTRUP and C. K. JORGENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1957, 11, 1223; (b) Y. TANABE and S. SUGANO, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.*, 1954, 9, 753, 766.
20. R. A. WALLON, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, 28, 2229.
21. K. C. PAILL and D. E. GOLDBERG, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1972, 34, 637.
22. W. MANCH and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1961, 38, 192.
23. A. B. P. LEVER, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1974, 51, 612.
24. B. N. FIGGIS and J. LEWIS, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1964, 6, 37.
25. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 357.
26. N. SAHA, K. M. DATTA and A. K. ADAK, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, 20, 745.
27. (a) F. K. KNEUBUHL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1960, 33, 1074; (b) I. M. PROCTOR, B. J. HATHWAY and P. NICHOLLS, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1678.
28. R. G. INSPEEK, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, 24, 763.
29. S. P. GHOSH, P. BHATTACHARJEE and L. K. MISHRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 308.
30. J. R. FERRARO, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1969, 23, 160.
31. M. MASHIMA, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 37, 974.
32. K. NAKAMOTO, Y. MORIMOTO and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4528.
33. L. KNORR and J. MACDONALD, *Ann. Chem.*, 1894, 279, 217.
34. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Analysis", ELBS, London, 1962, pp. 460, 568, 573.